

SOLUBILITIES OF WEAK ACIDS IN SALTS OF WEAK ACIDS.

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The solubilities of weak acids like benzoic acid and salicylic acid in sodium or potassium salts of various acids such as monochloroacetic acid, trichloroacetic acid, aminobenzoic acid, etc., have been determined. The observations are very similar to those made by Bhagwat and Doosag in case of other acids.

Bhagwat and Doosag (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 230) have determined the solubility of various weak acids in sodium salts of other weak acids. We have extended this work to various concentrations of salts of various weak acids such as monochloroacetic acid, trichloroacetic acid, benzenesulphonic acid, cinnamic acid, hippuric acid, etc., using benzoic acid and salicylic acid. From the results obtained and the graphs drawn following observations are made.

If we consider the solubilities of benzoic and salicylic acids in potassium salts of sulphanilic acid, phenylpropionic acid, glycollic acid, lactic acid, phenylacetic acid, *n*-butyric acid and *n*-propionic acid, we find that although the solubility of benzoic acid in pure water at the same temperature is greater than the solubility of salicylic acid, in potassium salts the solubility increases more rapidly for stronger salicylic acid than for benzoic acid. This is in accordance with the previous observations of Bhagwat and Doosag (*loc. cit.*). At a particular concentration of potassium salt, solubility of salicylic acid exceeds that of benzoic acid and then always remains greater than that of benzoic acid.

The solubility of benzoic acid and salicylic acid in the above mentioned salts shows a regularity except in the case of sulphanilic acid and phenylpropionic acid. The curves for the solubilities of benzoic and salicylic acids (not shown) in the case of phenylpropionic acid are somewhat irregular at low concentrations of potassium salts. After these concentrations they become regular. For sulphanilic acid, only the curve for the solubility of benzoic acid shows an irregularity at low concentrations. The concentrations of potassium salts at which the two curves meet are different for different acids and are in the following order: Phenylpropionic acid > *n*-butyric acid > propionic acid > sulphanilic acid > phenylacetic acid > lactic acid > glycollic acid.

The order of the dissociation constants of these acids are *n*-propionic acid (1.45×10^{-5}) < *n*-butyric acid (1.5×10^{-5}) < lactic acid (1.4×10^{-4}) < glycollic acid (1.4×10^{-4}).

From the results available it is concluded that the solubility of salicylic acid exceeds that of benzoic acid at lower concentrations in the salt solution of a stronger acid.

The solubilities of benzoic and salicylic acids in potassium salts of cinnamic and hippuric acids do not cut each other. However, in the case of cinnamic acid the two curves gradually approach each other. In other words, the solubility of salicylic acid increases more rapidly in the potassium salt than that of benzoic acid. Both the curves are similar and show a similar irregularity at low concentrations. Afterwards both become regular (curves not shown).

However, the curves of these acids in the potassium salt of hippuric acid are rather striking. Solubility of benzoic acid increases steadily, but the solubility of salicylic acid shows a break, and then rises only very slightly with increase in concentration of potassium salt of hippuric acid. Below this break, the solubility of salicylic acid increases more rapidly than that of benzoic acid and the two curves approach each other. However, beyond this point the curves go on diverging. In other words, the general rule that the solubility of a stronger acid increases at a greater rate than the solubility of weak acid in the same salt of an acid, seems to break down in case of this acid after certain point.

If we compare the solubility of a single acid in the solutions of potassium salts of different acids, it is observed that in general the solubility in the solution of the salt of a stronger acid is smaller, although deviations are common. Thus the order of the solubility of salicylic acid in salts of different acids is glycollic < lactic < *n*-butyric < *n*-propionic acid. The solubility curves in case of lactic acid and glycollic acid are rather striking. At low concentrations the solubilities are more or less the same. On increasing the concentration of potassium salt the solubility of salicylic acid in glycollic acid increases and then falls and finally becomes greater than the solubility in lactic acid.

Increase of concentration of potassium salt of hippuric and cinnamic acids does not seem to have an appreciable effect on the solubility of salicylic acid. The solubility in potassium phenylpropionate is smaller than in potassium hippurate for low concentrations. As the concentration is increased, the solubility of salicylic acid increases in potassium phenylpropionate. The order of solubility of salicylic acid in salts of different acids examined are as follows:—

n-Propionic acid > *n*-butyric acid > phenylacetic acid > lactic acid
> glycollic acid > sulphanilic acid > phenylpropionic acid > hippuric acid > cinnamic acid.

The order of solubility of benzoic acid in potassium salt of the same acids is more or less the same except for hippuric acid in whose salt benzoic acid is more soluble than even in the salts of glycollic and lactic acids. Moreover, the curve (not shown) indicates that the solubility increases fairly rapidly as the concentration of the potassium salt of hippuric acid is increased. This is unlike the solubility of salicylic acid which changes only slightly with increase in concentration. Behaviour in potassium cinnamate is very similar to that of salicylic acid. The order of the solubility of benzoic acid in potassium salts of various acids is as follows :—

Benzenesulphonic acid < cinnamic acid < phenylpropionic acid < sulphanic acid < glycollic acid < lactic acid < hippuric acid < phenylacetic acid < *n*-butyric acid < *n*-propionic acid.

The solubility of benzoic acid in sodium salts of monochloroacetic acid, trichloroacetic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid obeys the general rule, that the solubility is smaller in the salt of the stronger acid.

Solubility of both benzoic and salicylic acids in potassium salt of cinnamic acid shows an irregular curve at low concentrations. The solubility first increases, then decreases up to a point and again begins to increase regularly as the concentration of the potassium salt is increased. In potassium benzenesulphonate benzoic acid behaves similarly but there is one point of difference that solubility of benzoic acid decreases at first and then increases, afterwards becomes more or less constant and finally increases regularly as the concentration of potassium salt is increased.

Behaviour of potassium salt of 3 : 5-dinitrobenzoic acid is most peculiar. The solubility of benzoic acid first increases, becomes steady for a longer range, and then begins to fall as the concentration of the potassium salt is increased.